

Revealing Inclined Twin Related Defects in III-V Nanowires Grown in Popular Alternative Crystallographic Directions

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S2

Figure S2. 45 ° tilted SEM views of the (a) [100] InP and (b) <111> A GaAs nanowires. In the GaAs nanowires, only the vertical <111> A segment is analysed in this work and not the kinked part. Scale bars are 1 μm.

S3

Here we describe the method for ascertaining the shape of the defect planes using the dark field (DF) images. A sample that was annealed in-situ for 10 min at 550 °C following the growth procedure is used for this analysis, due to perfect octagonal cross section shape of these nanowires,¹ which facilitates ease of analysis. The DF images are acquired after tilting around the InP nanowire long axis from the conventional <110> zone axis. A DF image of a type 1 twin segment provides the projected shape of the octagonal {111} plane in the respective tilt angle. This shape is resized while maintaining the aspect ratio to compensate for tapering, and then used to calculate the projection angles, hence the respective directions and lengths on the thin {111} plane segment that contains the type 2 or 3 defect of interest. The shape of the type 2 or 3 defect is then re-produced on the {111} plane, accordingly, as shown in Figure 4 (d) and (e). Figure S3 provides few more examples of the shape and proposed position of type 2 and type 3 defects.

Figure S3. Examples of the shape and proposed position of type 2 and type 3 defects in [100] InP nanowires with respect to their {111} planes, which are marked by the red dashed lines as guides to the eye.

S4

Figure S4. Images at different magnifications of a type 2 twin defect in the $\langle 111 \rangle$ oriented segment of a $\langle 111 \rangle$ A GaAs nanowire. The clearly visible defect core is marked by a red arrow in (a), (b) and (c)i. Scale bar in (c) is 2 nm.

S5

Figure S5. Shape of type 2 twins in GaAs $\langle 111 \rangle$ A nanowires. The DF image is acquired after tilting the nanowire from the conventional $\langle 110 \rangle$ zone axis and shape of the tilted $\{111\}$ plane is deduced using the type 1 twin below (same process as in $[100]$ InP nanowires). By comparing with the projected shape and dimensions of the tilted $\{111\}$ plane, it could be seen that the type 2 twinned segment exists across the whole width in the viewing direction on the left-hand side. On the right-hand side, the defect-line forms a straight line that extends from one sidewall to another across the nanowire. Both these observations are contrary to those in $[100]$ InP nanowires where loops partially covered the $\{111\}$ plane in an irregular shape and the defect-line was not straight in the viewing direction. However, they are in agreement with the STEM observations of the type 2 defects in GaAs $\langle 111 \rangle$, where a clear defect core and twinned atom planes were observed.

S6

Figure S6. Images of a type 3 twin defect in the $\langle 111 \rangle$ oriented segment of a $\langle 111 \rangle$ A GaAs nanowire. In contrast to the $[100]$ nanowires, the type 3 defects in $\langle 111 \rangle$ A nanowires show a clear twin segment

in the middle and more abrupt transitions on either side. In the above example, the right-hand side (indicated by the red arrow) transition is sharp and edge-on, hence indicating that it exists across the whole or most of the diameter on that side. The left-hand side (indicated by the white arrow) is not as sharp as the right-hand side, but the blurred region is much shorter in width than those seen in [100] InP nanowires. White scale bar is 2 nm.

S7

Figure S7. BF images of an (a) intersection of two twin related defects that are viewed edge-on in a [100] nanowire, (b) intersection of an edge-on twin and another inclined twin in a <111> A oriented nanowire. Intersections will be at an angle to the viewing direction in <111> A nanowires since {111} planes will be at a 120° azimuthal angle to each other. In both the above examples, the propagation of one defect has been blocked by the other.

S8

Figure S8. (a) A TEM image close to the tip of a [100] InP nanowire. One completed (black arrow) and two just formed (red arrows) type 1 defects can be seen. The twinned segments extend across the diameter via the vapor-liquid-solid growth. (b) A BF STEM image showing the type 2 and 3 defect position in an InP [100] nanowire. Estimated VLS core size is marked by red dashed lines.

S9

Figure S9. BF image showing twin plane nucleation at lateral growth step edge in a [100] oriented InP nanowire. Red arrows indicate the plane that is oppositely twinned on the left and right hand-sides (left: untwined; right: twinned) due to it being independently twinned during lateral growth. Notice the blurred region formed in the middle (marked by a white arrow) due to the merging of the twinned nanowire crystal with the untwined main crystal on the left-hand side. The [100] growth direction of the nanowire is marked by the black arrow.

Figure S10: SEM, TEM and STEM images of defect-free [100] and <111> A nanowires. (a) 45° tilted SEM view of [100] InP nanowires grown under the same growth conditions as those in Figure S2 (a), but with one-third the flow rates for both group III and V (TMIn flow rate was 1.62×10^{-5} mol/min; growth time was scaled to 30 min accordingly). (b) Low and high magnification TEM images of a nanowire from the same sample showing the absence of twins. Despite also being tapered, the lateral unintentional shell growth has now reduced to ~ 3 nm/min in the new defect-free sample. (c) 45° tilted SEM view of <111> A GaAs nanowires grown under same growth conditions as those in Figure S2 (b), but at a temperature of 420 °C and catalysed by 100 nm Au particles. Note that kinking, which was linked to inclined twins, is also eliminated in these nanowires². (d) Low and high magnification, respective BF and ADF STEM images of a nanowire from the same sample showing the absence of twins. All unlabelled scale bars are 1 μm.

Figure S11: Optical emissions of defective and defect-free [100] InP nanowires. (a) RT μ -PL spectra along another typical defect-free nanowire ($\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$ long) similar to the one of Figure 5 (a). Here, each spectrum is normalized to its maximum intensity, which shows that the PL lineshape does not vary along the nanowire. (b) Same as in panel (a), for a typical $\sim 4.5 \mu\text{m}$ long defective nanowire, similar to the one discussed in Figure 5 (b). (c) Integrated intensity normalized by the local cross-sectional area as a function of position for four different defect-free nanowires (the NW whose spectra are displayed in panel (a) here is NW02). The average results are plotted in Figure 5 (d) in the main text. (d) Same as (c), but for three different defective nanowires (the NW whose spectra are displayed in panel (b) here is NW03)). Overall, these data demonstrate the high reproducibility of the experimental results discussed in Figure 5.

References:

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2. Yuan, X.; Caroff, P.; Wong-Leung, J.; Fu, L., et al. Tunable Polarity in a III-V Nanowire by Droplet Wetting and Surface Energy Engineering. *Advanced Materials* 2015, 27, 6096-6103.